
ELECTORAL BONDS: SERIOUS IMPACT ON TRANSPARENCY TO GETTING SCRAPED

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ABSTRACT

Indian democracy is characterized by a parliament with multifarious political parties as they are the key players in Indian politics. Democracy is created on free and fair elections. Electoral bonds in India are a financial instrument introduced in 2018, for ensuring transparency in political funding. These are used for funding political parties in India, which have sparked considerable debate regarding their impact on the transparency of political donations. As a measure to clean up political funding from anonymizing donor identities, thus protecting them from potential backlash, these bonds have raised concerns about the erosion of transparency in political finance. Critics contended that by it would lead to opacity, and by allowing donors to remain anonymous, electoral bonds provide a legal avenue for corporates and individuals to influence political parties and policies without public scrutiny. On 15th February 2024, a five-judge bench comprising chief justice of India DY Chandrachud, delivered a unanimous verdict by scrapping the electoral bonds scheme.

Keywords: Electoral bonds, Free and Fair elections, Transparency, Opacity.

I. INTRODUCTION

On 1st February 2017, late MR Arun Jaitley in union budget session promised to get transparency in electoral funding by allowing donors to contribute anonymously to political parties. By passing of the finance bill, electoral bonds were introduced. An electoral bond has been issued as a promissory note, which can be purchased by any individual, company, or organization from State bank of India and then donated to a political party of donor's

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choice. These donations or bonds are similar to banknotes in which they have non-interest bearing and receivable to banker on demand which are redeemed in designated accounts of political parties within 15 days. Any person complying with know your customer's (KYC) requirements is able to acquire these bonds. The bonds can be lent at value of Rs1000, Rs10000, Rs100000, Rs10 Lakh, or Rs1 Crore. As on any currency note, date, and amount of the currency is mentioned by RBI, similarly date of publication and value of bond is mentioned on the promissory note. The electoral bonds scheme has opened the floodgates to unlimited donations by any individual, corporate entity, or Hindu undivided family to State bank of India to purchase electoral bonds any number of times at any value. The electoral bond also contains a unique code that helps the State bank of India to track the bond. An amendment was brought by central government in four acts namely, Representation of People Act, 1951 (RPA), Income Tax Act, 1961, Foreign Contributions Regulation Act, 2010 (FCRA), to introduce the Electoral bonds scheme via the Finance acts of 2016 and 2017. Electoral bonds are exclusively for the parties that are registered under Section 29A of the Representation of People Act, 1951 and to the parties that have received at least one per cent of the vote in the most recent General or Assembly elections. These electoral bonds are lent for purchase only for 10 days in the months of January, April, July, October. During the Lok Sabha elections these bonds can be notified for an additional 30 days by the central government.

While introducing the scheme the then finance minister Mr. Arun Jaitley's main reform was to have accounted and legal money for funding political parties and to eliminate the influx of black money from election funding. This scheme offers the best way to protect the donors' rights while making donations digitally through electronically issued bonds. But the court observed that bonds have been targeted for infusing opacity in the political – funding system. So, on 15th February 2024, the court announced its verdict calling for the bonds to be scrapped. The scheme has been under scrutiny, and the top court had in November said that the bonds “put a premium on opacity” and can be “misused for money laundering.”

II. FUNDINGS IN ELECTIONS

Previously, it was mandatory to report the names and other details of the donors who contributed more than 20,000 Rs towards the political parties while filling Income tax reports

(ITR). Donations below Rs 20,000 were declared as donations from unknown sources. In 2019 general elections would have the heaviest corporate exposure in terms of political fundings and influence narratives. A major change affecting corporate donations was brought in 2013 by amending the companies act. The limit of 5 per cent was raised and corporate donors were allowed to donate up to 7.5 per cent of the net average profits earned in the preceding three years. Earlier in 1969, Indira Gandhi government imposed a complete ban on corporate funding (by deletion of the Section 293A of the Companies act) to check the popularity of the center-right Swatantra Party by drying it off the finances. Through these the rise of “briefcase politics” was seen by which vast amount of black money was transferred into Congress party account. Later, by taking a crucial decision the ban was lifted by Rajiv Gandhi government in 1985.

According to the report of Association of Democratic Reforms (ADR) in 2017 the total income of political parties in India between 2004-2005 and 2014-2015 was Rs 11,367 crore and 69% income amounting to Rs 7,833 came from unknown sources. Only 16% of the total income was from unknown donor.

Figure 1: Total income from FY 17-18 to FY 22-23

A total of Rs 276.2 Crore was donated for national parties from Delhi, followed by Rs 160.2 crore from Gujarat, and 96.27 crore from Maharashtra. A total of Rs 22.34 crore (2.63% of total donations received) could not be attributed to any state or any Union Territory due to

incomplete/undeclared information provided by parties. From around 3,318 corporate/commercial sector 680.49 crore donation was made which is 80% of the total donation. The remaining 20% donation was made by individual donors which was 166.62 crore.

Figure 2: Donations from corporate and individual donors

In 2022-2023 a total of 3,067 donations from corporate/business sectors was made to the BJP (Rs 610.29 crore) while 4,612 individual donors donated Rs 106.72 crore to the party. Congress received a total of 55.62 crore from 70 donations from corporate/business sector and 24.24 crore from 823 individual donors.

III. POLITICAL FUNDINGS IN WORLDS LARGEST ECONOMY:

United States of America (USA) is the oldest modern democracy in the world. In 1971, the US Congress enacted the Federal Election Campaign Act (FECA), which brought in more stringent disclosure requirements for federal candidates, political parties & Political action committees (PACs). Further limits were set on contributions by individuals, political parties, and PACs by bringing amendment in 1974. The next amendment was made through the Bipartisan Campaign Reform Act of 2002 (BCRA) which banned national political parties from raising or spending non – federal funds. In 2010 in Citizens United Vs FEC, Supreme Court struck down the limit on the ability of organizations FEC allows contributions from individuals, certain limited liability companies, political action committees (PACs), non-connected PACs. On the other side contributions from corporations, Labor Organizations, foreign government contractors

cannot contribute according to FEC rules. Limits specified for contributions is \$100 on cash contribution from particular source, \$50 on anonymous contributions. In every Presidential election the record of political funding keeps increasing. In the recent 2020 elections Sanjeev Joshipura who lead the Indians for Biden campaign said that “In America money ends up being the mother’s milk of politics”.

Political parties in the United Kingdom are not entitled to large-scale public funding, unlike their counterparts in many comparable democracies. Donations for funding can come from individuals, companies, trade unions, and other organizations. Donations might be monetary or non-monetary. The House of Commons and the House of Lords both provide opposition parties with funding to support their parliamentary duties. In the house of commons, this is known as Short Money. In the House of Lords, it is known as Cranborne Money. There is no limit to the amount to be donated, but donors must be registered in some circumstances. Parties must declare financing if it exceeds £7,500 to the central party or £1,500 to accounting units according to the UK Electoral Commission. If any unincorporated association donates more than £25,000 to a political party, individual, or other organization in a year.

In India, there is no transparency regarding the donation and identity of the individual which can be seen in the UK and USA not completely but to a greater extent than in India.

IV. BONDS GETTING SCRAPPED

On 15th February 2024, the Supreme Court scrapped electoral bonds calling them unconstitutional. The debate around electoral bonds has led to calls for their scrapping, with critics arguing for a return to more transparent modes of political funding. Supreme Courts five-judge bench including CJI DY Chandrachud, and justices Sanjiv Khanna, BR Gavai, JB Pardiwala, and Manoj Mishra pronounced the judgement. The criticism for this started in 2017. An NGO ‘Association for democratic reforms’, lead petitioner, moved to Supreme Court challenging the scheme. On this Supreme Court sends summons to center and Election Commission on PIL filed by the NGO. On this, on November 7, 2022, the electoral bond scheme was amended, and the sales days were increased from 70 to 85 days in a year where any assembly election may be scheduled. On October 16, 2023, the bench headed by CJI refers plea s against the scheme to a five-judge constitution bench. Electoral bonds, mainly issued in

high denominations, raise concerns of corporate dominance over individual donors, and the anonymity for donors further feels suspicious. Prashant Bhushan representing the NGO Association for Democratic Reforms (ADR), argued that adjudication is necessary before using the electoral bond scheme in 2024 general elections. Activist Lokesh Batra who filled an RTI revealed that the Ministry of Finance implemented changes to scheme without consulting the Election Commission. RBI also expressed disagreement towards the scheme, regarding concerns about money laundering and the potential misuse of electoral bonds.

The court said that the electoral bonds scheme violates the right to information and freedom of speech and expression under Article 19(1)(a) of the constitution which can lead to quid pro quo. The amendment to the Companies Act which allows blanket corporate political funding is unconstitutional. The state bank of India (SBI) was asked to immediately stop issuing it. SBI shall furnish bonds purchase details with date of purchase, name of purchaser, denomination. The election commission of India (ECI) was asked to publish the details on its official website by March 14, 2024. The court said that electoral bonds which are not encashed by political parties shall be returned and refunded to purchasers. The bank has to refund the purchasing party after the uncashed bonds are returned.

On March 14, 2024 the Election Commission of India lists revealing the names of the buyers and bonds purchased between April 12, 2019, to January 2024 and the amount of each bond encashed by political parties. The largest beneficiary of the opaque funding tool has been Bhartiya Janta Party who received Rs 8251.8 crore through the scheme, out of the total bonds sold worth about Rs 16,518 crore. BJP redeemed around 50% of all bonds sold. Congress got Rs 1952 crore worth of bonds redeemed constituting around 47.5% of the total bonds uncashed by parties. The Trinamool congress was at third place with Rs 1,705 crore. The top donors includes the biggest Business Tycoons and the top industrialists. according to the data Future gaming & Hotel Services Pvt Ltd led by the prominent figure Santiago Martin merged as the most substantial donor to political parties. More than 22 entities contributed around more than 100 crores during this period. Among them were Megha Engineering & Infrastructure limited by donating Rs 966 crores, Qwik Supply Chain with Rs 410 crores, Haldia Energy Limited with Rs 377 crores, Vedanta Limited with Rs 375.65 crores, Essel mining and industries limited with Rs 244.45 crores, Bharti Airtel Ltd with Rs 198 crores and Keventer food Infra Ltd with Rs 195 crores. Major purchases of electoral bonds includes Grasim Industries, Piramal Enterprises, Torrent Power, DLF Commercial Developers, Apollo Tyres, Lakshmi Mittal, PVR, Sula Wine, Welspun, Sun Pharma. After this supreme court asked the State Bank of India

to submit data with the “Alphanumeric Number” of all bonds purchased and redeemed. Once the codes are known, it will become possible to map donors to recipients, revealing who gave money to which party.

V. CONCLUSION

Electoral bonds were taken into consideration to uplift the democratic values and to cherish the elections to make them more transparent, but the present scenario and process have made it opaque which made it opaque which lead to political corruption. The government’s electoral bond system has so far failed to provide the required results. As the ban is imposed it would enhance political transparency fostering a clearer understanding of potential influences on policy decisions. Public trust in democracy will be strengthened as they will have confidence that elected officials will act in the public’s interest rather than swayed by anonymous donors. The effectiveness of banning electoral bonds in achieving these goals depends significantly on the alternative mechanisms put in place. The success of such a ban would require robust systems for transparency, accountability, and enforcement to ensure that political financing is both transparent and fair.

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